

Corrosion behavior in liquid lead of a novel FCC non-equiatomic high-entropy alloy capable of forming an alumina protective oxide scale

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ABSTRACT

This study presents the design, characterization and evaluation of corrosion resistance and mechanical integrity of a novel Co-free face-centered cubic (FCC) non-equiatomic $\text{Fe}_{33.5}\text{Ni}_{43.5}\text{Cr}_{11}\text{Mn}_6\text{Al}_6$ High-Entropy Alloy (HEA) for structural applications in Generation IV Lead-cooled Fast Reactors (LFRs). The alloy was engineered to form a protective Al-rich oxide scale. Liquid Metal Corrosion (LMC) tests were conducted in stagnant liquid Pb at 550 °C and 650 °C for 1150 h, under controlled oxygen concentrations ranging from $7.4 \cdot 10^{-6}$ to $8.6 \cdot 10^{-6}$ wt% at 550 °C, and from $4.5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ to $3.6 \cdot 10^{-4}$ wt% at 650 °C. Liquid Metal Embrittlement (LME) susceptibility was assessed via Slow Strain Rate Testing (SSRT) between 350 °C to 600 °C. LMC test results revealed bilayer oxide scale formation, with an inner amorphous alumina scale acting as an effective diffusion barrier and a complex outer Mn (Al,Fe,Cr)₂O₄ spinel prone to detachment. The alloy exhibited self-healing behavior, regenerating protective oxides in areas where Pb penetration took place. No signs of LME were observed up to 400 °C, with embrittlement onset occurring at 500 °C. Despite its high Ni content, which is typically detrimental in liquid Pb due to its high solubility at elevated temperatures, leading to accelerated degradation, combined with low oxygen availability that hinders protective oxide formation and microstructural heterogeneities (oxide inclusions and local grain size variations), the alloy maintained excellent corrosion resistance and mechanical integrity. These results underscore the exceptional corrosion resistance of this non-equiatomic $\text{Fe}_{33.5}\text{Ni}_{43.5}\text{Cr}_{11}\text{Mn}_6\text{Al}_6$ HEA, positioning it as a highly promising candidate for high-temperature nuclear applications in Pb-cooled systems.

1. Introduction

Generation IV nuclear reactors are expected to play a key role in the future energy landscape. However, as highlighted by Locatelli et al., political, strategic, and economic constraints will likely prevent many of these designs from reaching commercial deployment [1]. Among them, LFRs stand out due to the exceptional properties of Pb and Lead-Bismuth Eutectic (LBE) as heavy liquid metal (HLM) coolants.

These coolants offer minimal neutron moderation and absorption, making them ideal for fast-spectrum reactors, which can generate more fuel and reduce nuclear waste [2–4]. In addition, both Pb and LBE are

chemically inert, avoiding a violent interaction with air or water [3–6]. The high thermal conductivity of Pb allows a more efficient heat removal and improved reactor safety and performance. Pb also enables high operating temperatures, typically 400 °C at the core inlet and 550 °C at the outlet, with local peaks up to 650 °C [5], which improves thermal efficiency. The high boiling point of Pb prevents its boiling even under extreme conditions, enhancing passive safety [5,7,8]. However, the use of Pb and LBE also presents challenges, such as the corrosion of structural materials, sensitivity to oxygen concentration, and potential embrittlement under certain mechanical and thermal conditions. For this reason, a large effort is focused on the development of materials

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with a protective scale that can mitigate any degradation mechanisms [3].

Any candidate material for LFR applications is required to not only minimize its impact as nuclear waste, but to not suffer degradation by radiation, minimize the impact that phase transformations could have at high operating temperatures, maintain or enhance mechanical properties and reduce susceptibility to Liquid Metal Corrosion (LMC) and Liquid Metal Embrittlement (LME). In fact, LMC and LME are the two most important mechanisms of materials degradation in Pb and LBE [3]. LMC refers to the degradation of structural materials due to chemical interactions with an HLM. It typically involves selective dissolution of alloying elements and it is influenced by temperature, exposure time, oxygen concentration, metal flow if it is not stagnant, and the alloy's ability to form protective oxide scales [9]. The LMC normally manifests as localized penetration in a preexisting microstructural feature, such as twin and grain boundaries, precipitates, inclusions or regions of chemical segregation. On the other hand, the LME phenomenon is a mechanical degradation that occurs when ductile alloys become brittle due to exposure to HLM under mechanical stress. Unlike LMC, LME involves the penetration of the liquid metal along grain boundaries, twins, dislocations, precipitates, normally leading to intergranular fracture. This embrittlement is typically sudden and can occur even at relatively low temperatures [3].

Even though oxide scales are essential for protecting alloys from aggressive environments, not all oxide scales provide the same level of protection. Their effectiveness can vary depending on factors such as thickness, density, and the presence of defects [3]. Ideally, a protective scale should be thin, to minimize internal stresses that could lead to detachment from the surface; dense, to prevent the penetration of the aggressive environment through the scale; and continuous and free of defects, to avoid preferential pathways for corrosion [3]. However, not all oxides work for those applications; for example, in conventional stainless steels based on Cr oxide, the Cr_2O_3 formed has been reported to be vulnerable in LMC conditions for temperatures above 450 °C. This is due to the corrosion dissolution of Ni, Mn and Cr in the liquid metal which severely increases at rising the temperature, making the protective stable scale formation inefficient in Pb or LBE [9,10]. In fact, studies in a 316 L alloy at 450 °C have reported that maintaining an adequate and stable level of oxygen in the liquid metal is crucial to prevent the dissolution of the alloy, and above that temperature, the thickness of the scale becomes a limiting factor [11]. Not only in HLMs do the conventional alloys have problems; under steam conditions the Cr oxide scale is also unstable and turns into volatile oxy-hydroxides [12,13]. For this reason, the achievement of continuous, thin and slow growth alumina scales concentrates most of the current alloy developments [12,14], which, given their strong chemical stability and limited atomic mobility can withstand adverse environments at high temperature [15,16].

Despite the growing interest in High Entropy Alloys (HEAs) and their potential good properties under irradiation, as for instance low volume swelling for HEAs with FCC structure as compared to austenitic steels [17,18], limited studies have addressed their behavior under LMC and LME, particularly in FCC-structured HEAs exposed to liquid Pb or LBE. This is largely due to the high Ni content required to stabilize the FCC phase, which also increases the alloy's solubility in Pb-based environments. Among the few notable investigations evaluating the behavior of FCC-structured HEAs in environments relating to LFRs, most have focused on LME using Slow Strain Rate Testing (SSRT) in LBE. For example, the non-equiatomic FCC $\text{Fe}_{40}\text{Mn}_{10}\text{Ni}_{10}\text{Co}_{20}\text{Cr}_{20}$ HEA demonstrated promising resistance to LME at 250 °C and 350 °C [19]. Similarly, an FCC-based HEAs with minor B2-phase $\text{Al}_{0.4}\text{CoCrFeNi}$ HEA exhibited LME only at 500 °C, but not at 350 °C [20]. In terms of LMC, tests in LBE at 550 °C for up to 1000 h on an FCC-based HEAs with minor B2-phase initial microstructure, such as $\text{Fe}_{45}\text{Ni}_{30-x}\text{Cr}_{15}\text{Al}_{10}\text{Ti}_x$ ($x = 3, 4$ and 5 at%), revealed the formation of a dual-layer oxide scale. This consisted of an outer FeCr_2O_4 spinel and an inner layer comprising Cr_2O_3 , Al_2O_3 and TiO_2 , which provided effective protection against LMC

[21]. Additionally, HEAs have been explored as protective coatings applied via laser cladding. For instance, an [20] FCC with minor Laves phase AlCrFeNiNb HEA coatings developed a Cr-rich spinel scale after 1000 h at 550 °C [22].

The potential of HEAs has been demonstrated in results such as those reported by Hao Shi et al. where systematic alloy screening of various HEAs with protective scales was performed, including single-phase FCC alloys and others containing additional phases in the as-cast condition under different aggressive environments. On the one hand, Hao Shi et al. evaluated the oxidation resistance in steam at 1200 °C of different single and multiphase HEAs with protective scales, exhibiting excellent oxidation resistance forming a continuous and highly protective alumina scale [23]. This behavior is observed not only in single-phase FCC HEAs such as $\text{Al}_{7.9}\text{Cr}_{23.2}\text{Fe}_{34.1}\text{Ni}_{34.8}$, but also in multiphase HEAs like $\text{Al}_{8.2}\text{Cr}_{21.4}\text{Fe}_{30.3}\text{Ni}_{35}\text{Nb}_{5.1}$, which includes an FCC matrix and Laves phase (Fe_2Nb). On the other hand, two additional separate studies were carried out by Hao Shi et al. in oxygen-containing liquid Pb at 600 °C for up to 2000 h. Among the single-phase FCC alloys, $\text{Al}_8\text{Cr}_{22}\text{Fe}_{32}\text{Ni}_{33}\text{Cu}_5$ developed an outer $\text{Fe}(\text{Cr},\text{Al})_2\text{O}_4$ spinel layer and an inner Al_2O_3 scale, though with poor adhesion due to Cu segregation at the oxide/matrix interface [24]. In contrast, other FCC alloys such as $\text{Al}_6\text{Cr}_{25}\text{Fe}_{34}\text{Ni}_{35}$ and $\text{Al}_8\text{Cr}_{23.2}\text{Fe}_{34}\text{Ni}_{34.8}$ formed well-adhered Cr_2O_3 and $(\text{Al},\text{Cr})_2\text{O}_3$ scales, showing no signs of Pb-induced attack. Notably, multiphase HEAs, such as $\text{Al}_{7.9}\text{Cr}_{22}\text{Fe}_{31.9}\text{Ni}_{33.2}\text{Ti}_5$ (FCC + BCC + B2-Ni(Al,Ti)) and $\text{Al}_{8.2}\text{Cr}_{21.4}\text{Fe}_{30.3}\text{Ni}_{35}\text{Nb}_{5.1}$ (FCC + Laves + B2-NiAl) exhibited enhanced corrosion resistance. In particular, the Nb-containing alloy developed a well-adhered bilayer oxide scale, consisting of an outer Cr_2O_3 layer and an inner Al_2O_3 layer, which remained protective even after 2000 h of exposure [25].

In this work, a novel Co-free non-equiatomic $\text{Fe}_{33.5}\text{Ni}_{43.5}\text{Cr}_{11}\text{Mn}_6\text{Al}_6$ FCC-HEA was designed with two main objectives: to be suitable for nuclear applications by avoiding elements prone to activation under irradiation, and to form a protective scale. To assess its applicability in LFR environments and study the formation of self-healing Al-rich oxide scale, the alloy was subjected to LMC tests in stagnant molten Pb at 550 °C, close to typical operating temperatures, and at 650 °C, a higher temperature that mimics the temperature rise in case an incident that may happens to the reactor, to test the scale stability in such condition. Additionally, the alloy's resistance to LME was investigated through SSRT tests conducted in molten Pb across a temperature range from 350 °C to 600 °C. These two tests are independent by design but complementary. LMC tests long-term corrosion and oxide-scale stability under controlled oxygen and temperature while SSRT targets short-time, stress-assisted degradation under boundary conditions that delay protective-scale development and maximize LME sensitivity. Using both tests allows for the decoupling of the thermodynamic/kinetic stability of the oxide barrier from the mechanical integrity of the alloy when the early-stage oxide is still discontinuous, which is critical for LFRs. Moreover, in this work the thermal stability of the $\text{Fe}_{33.5}\text{Ni}_{43.5}\text{Cr}_{11}\text{Mn}_6\text{Al}_6$ FCC-HEA microstructure and the evolution of phases during exposure was studied in order to ensure long-term performance in LFR environments.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Alloy processing and treatments

The alloy was produced externally at the Tecnalia Research Center using induction casting facilities [26]. Ingots were cut from an initial truncated pyramid, resulting in pieces with 20 mm thickness. These ingots underwent a solubilization treatment consisting of 4 h at 1100 °C followed by 4 h at 1200 °C, then quenched in water. Subsequently, the material was cold rolled with a 50 % thickness reduction, performed in 20 steps. Finally, the alloy was subjected to an annealing heat treatment at 925 °C for 15 min

2.2. Microstructural and chemical characterization

Metallic chips extracted from the annealed strip were used to determine its chemical composition by Inductively Coupled Plasma Optical Emission Spectroscopy (ICP-OES) using an Agilent 5100 ICP-OES spectrometer. The phases present on both, bulk material and superficial oxide layers were determined from the X ray diffraction (XRD) patterns recorded with a Bruker AXS D8 Discover diffractometer equipped with a Co X-ray tube. XRD data were collected in both, conventional Bragg-Brentano geometry to determine the phases present on the bulk material and under grazing incidence condition keeping the incidence beam angle at 2° for characterization of the corrosion products present in the outermost scale. Evaluation of the elemental distribution on the alloy near the surface and fracture surface analysis were carried out with a Hitachi S-4800 cold field emission scanning electron microscope equipped with an Oxford SDD Xmax20 microanalysis system for EDS line scans. Additionally, Electron Probe Microanalysis (EPMA) was conducted using a JEOL JXA-iHP200F microprobe with four Wavelength Dispersive Spectrometers (WDS), operating at 20 kV and an increased current of 200 nA, maintaining the same acquisition time. Finally, microhardness measurements were performed using a Struers DuraVista-40 automated microhardness tester equipped with a Vickers indenter.

2.3. Samples preparation

For basic characterization, annealed specimens were sectioned, to expose the plane perpendicular to the rolling direction (RD), and mounted in black bakelite with a carbon filler. The samples were ground using progressively finer silicon carbide papers (P320, P600, P1200, and P2000), followed by mechanical polishing with an automatic metallographic polisher. A $3\ \mu\text{m}$ water-based diamond suspension was applied using a taffeta cloth, and a final polishing step was performed using a $0.04\ \mu\text{m}$ colloidal silica suspension on a porous neoprene cloth.

2.4. Liquid metal corrosion (LMC) testing

To study the LMC behavior of the $\text{Fe}_{33.5}\text{Ni}_{43.5}\text{Cr}_{11}\text{Mn}_6\text{Al}_6$ HEA in stagnant liquid Pb, the alloy was tested at 550°C and 650°C for 1150 h exposure times, in order to evaluate the oxidation progression and the protective scale formation. Two samples were tested for each condition.

All samples were manufactured with dimensions of $40 \times 5 \times 3\ \text{mm}^3$, with the largest dimension along the RD. Prior to testing, the samples were ground with P600 silicon carbide paper to activate the surface and eliminate any defects that could promote preferential penetration. The ground samples were then immersed in alumina crucibles filled with preheated molten Pb, ensuring that most of the sample was submerged. The crucibles were placed in the COSTA (CORrosion test facility for STagnant liquid Alloys) furnace at KTH. This facility allows precise control of the oxygen partial pressure by adjusting the $\text{Ar-H}_2\text{-H}_2\text{O}$ gas mixture, preventing the formation of unwanted oxides: Ar-H_2 was used to reduce the O_2 content, and $\text{Ar-H}_2\text{O}$ to increase it. Additionally, a ZIROX SGM5 oxygen sensor was employed to monitor and confirm the oxygen levels during the test. The parameters used and measured for the two experiments are shown in Table 1.

After exposure, excess solidified lead was removed chemically by immersing the samples in a solution of hydrogen peroxide, acetic acid,

Table 1

Experimental test values used at 550°C and 650°C in the stagnant liquid Pb exposures of HEA $\text{Fe}_{33.5}\text{Ni}_{43.5}\text{Cr}_{11}\text{Mn}_6\text{Al}_6$.

Temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$)	$\text{H}_2/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ Ratio	pO_2 (bar)	Dissolved O_2 in Pb (wt%)
550	$(2.23\text{--}2.00) \times 10^{-2}$	$(5.07\text{--}3.73) \times 10^{-23}$	$(8.58\text{--}7.35) \times 10^{-6}$
650	$(1.67\text{--}0.21) \times 10^{-2}$	$(1.12\text{--}0.02) \times 10^{-17}$	$(3.63\text{--}0.45) \times 10^{-4}$

and water (1:1:7 ratio) for up to 45 min. Following this cleaning step, two sections of approximately $5 \times 5 \times 3\ \text{mm}^3$ were extracted from each same sample. The cuts were made perpendicular to the RD, with the 5 mm dimension aligned along the RD. The first section, taken from the side not exposed to the molten lead, was mounted in transparent acrylic resin for XRD analysis to evaluate the thermal stability of the alloy and identify the phases present in the bulk. The second section, taken from the exposed side, was mounted in black bakelite to analyze the Pb-alloy interface and assess the formation of the protective scale. Both samples were polished following the same mechanical polishing procedure described for the basic characterization. The remaining part of the sample was used to perform Grazing Incidence X-Ray Diffraction (GIXRD) on the surface to evaluate the nature of the oxides formed. For nanoscale cross-sectional characterization of the oxide scale, site-specific lamellae were extracted from the oxidized surface using an FEI Helios NanoLab 600 dual-beam Focused Ion Beam - Scanning electron microscope (FIB-SEM). The lamellae were analyzed with a JEOL JEM 3000 F Scanning Transmission Electron Microscope (STEM) operated at 300 kV, with a High Angle Annular Dark-Field (HAADF) detector.

2.5. Liquid metal embrittlement (LME) testing

To investigate the LME phenomenon in the non-equiatomic $\text{Fe}_{33.5}\text{Ni}_{43.5}\text{Cr}_{11}\text{Mn}_6\text{Al}_6$ HEA in stagnant liquid Pb, SSRT was used, which consists of a uniaxial tensile test performed at a very low strain rate ($5 \cdot 10^{-5}\ \text{mm/s}$) to enhance material-environment interactions and facilitate the detection of embrittlement and other degradation mechanisms. For this goal, non-standard cylindrical tensile test pieces were machined parallel to the rolling direction with an overall length of 36 mm, a circular grip cross-section with a diameter of 4 mm, a gauge length of 12 mm and a diameter of 2 mm.

SSRTs were performed at 350°C , 400°C , 500°C and $580/600^\circ\text{C}$ for two environments: in the first environment, specimens were immersed in liquid Pb and Ar-H_2 atmosphere following a pre-exposure treatment at 450°C for $\sim 22\text{h}$ to ensure proper wetting between the sample surface and the liquid metal as reported in similar studies in liquid Pb [10] or LBE [8,10]; the second condition used Ar as an inert control medium, without any pre-exposure heat treatment. It has been confirmed that the pre-exposure ageing treatment at 450°C for 22 h in liquid Pb does not induce any detectable microstructural changes, such as precipitation or grain growth, nor does it increase hardness. This ensures that the mechanical response during testing remains unaffected and that the results are not masked. It also allows for a reliable comparison with tests conducted in the Ar inert atmosphere, where no pre-exposure treatment was applied.

The SSRT rig used in the experiments was developed at KTH. This custom-built apparatus is capable of operating at temperatures up to 620°C in liquid lead and 580°C in inert gas environments. To minimize oxidation and maintain a low oxygen partial pressure, the system was purged with a mixture of Ar-5\% H_2 , achieving an oxygen concentration of approximately $10^{-11}\ \text{wt\%}$. This low oxygen concentration was used to maximize the aggressiveness of the environment. This extreme condition promotes the degradation of the oxide scale, thereby facilitating liquid metal penetration and allowing the evaluation of the behavior of the material under the worst scenario.

To evaluate the failure mechanisms, the fracture surfaces of the SSRT specimens were inspected using scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Prior to observation, excess solidified Pb was chemically removed by immersing the specimens in a solution of hydrogen peroxide, acetic acid, and water (1:1:7 ratio) for up to 45 min. To analyze crack initiation and propagation, Electron Backscatter Diffraction (EBSD) was performed on metallographically polished cross-sections using a JEOL JSM-6500F field-emission SEM equipped with an Oxford Instruments EBSD detector (C-Nano+). Maps were acquired with a step size of $0.28\ \mu\text{m}$. Post-processing was carried out in MTEX (MATLAB) [27].

Table 2Nominal and experimental composition of the Fe_{33.5}Ni_{43.5}Cr₁₁Mn₆Al₆ HEA measured using Inductively Coupled Plasma Optical Emission Spectroscopy (ICP-OES).

Composition	Al	Cr	Fe	Mn	Ni	C
wt%						
Nominal	2.95	10.42	34.09	6.01	46.53	-
Experimental	2.81 ± 0.02	10.25 ± 0.04	34.25 ± 0.19	6.26 ± 0.04	46.40 ± 0.27	0.03 ± 0.01
at%						
Nominal	6	11	33.5	6	43.5	-
Experimental	5.72 ± 0.05	10.82 ± 0.08	33.67 ± 0.28	6.26 ± 0.06	43.40 ± 0.37	0.14 ± 0.05

3. Alloy design

To develop a fFCC HEA with a protective scale intended for structural applications in Generation IV LFRs, several key criteria must be considered, including the appropriate selection and proportion of alloying elements required to form a protective Al-rich oxide scale, as well as the activation behavior of these elements under neutron irradiation. This design framework is detailed hereinafter and was subsequently refined using CALPHAD calculations performed with ThermoCalc® 2023b software (TCHEA6 database), to tailor FCC phase stability, prevent the formation of brittle phases, promote the precipitation of strengthening phases such as L1₂, and adapt the composition to the specific characteristics of the HEA system under investigation.

In order to withstand high-temperature oxidation and aggressive environments induced by liquid Pb or LBE, it is critical to form a barrier against those conditions, such as a stable and protective scale. Given that the development of FCC HEAs with a protective scale is still in its early stages, their design must draw upon the well-established principles of alumina forming austenitic (AFA) steels, a stainless-steel family capable of forming an alumina (Al₂O₃) scale, ideally formed as α-Al₂O₃, which is the most protective alumina layer. When temperature is not high enough to stabilize α-Al₂O₃, other alumina scales that can form are γ, θ, and δ; these can also appear as a transitional phase of α-Al₂O₃. The γ-, θ-, and δ-Al₂O₃ scales have minor stability and protectiveness compared to α-Al₂O₃ [14]. According to several studies, the amount of Al needed to achieve this protective behavior requires an Al content above than 2.5 wt% (or equivalently around 5 at%) [23,28]. However, Al alone is insufficient to ensure the formation of a stable and protective alumina layer. Cr plays a vital complementary role. Several studies have shown that Cr acts as an oxygen getter, reducing the required Al content by slowing the inward diffusion of oxygen into the alloy matrix, a phenomenon commonly referred to as the third element effect [12,29,30]. This not only suppresses internal oxidation but also promotes the formation of the thermodynamically stable α-Al₂O₃ phase over the less protective metastable γ-Al₂O₃. According to the findings of Y. Niu [31, 32], as little as 10 at% Cr is sufficient to promote the development of a durable alumina scale that effectively limits corrosion progression. Due to the strong ferrite-forming tendencies of Al and Cr, AFA steels typically require high Ni content to stabilize the austenitic phase [23]. This reliance on the alumina scale formation is particularly important in liquid Pb or LBE environments, where high solubility is exhibited for Ni in Pb [4,33] and LBE [4]. Other alloying elements, such as Mn, have also been reported to contribute to the formation of alumina-rich protective scales. Under oxidation conditions in the 700–800 °C range, Mn-enriched alumina scales have been observed, suggesting a potential synergistic effect in multicomponent systems [12].

To design alloys suitable for nuclear applications, it is essential to consider their activation behavior under irradiation, particularly the half-life of the resulting alloy. To assess which elements, exhibit higher or lower activation levels, reference data were consulted from the Handbook on Nuclear Activation Data [34]. For instance, although Co significantly enhances mechanical strength and hardness, it is typically excluded due to its high activation under neutron irradiation. The primary isotope, ⁶⁰Co, has a half-life of 5.27 years and emits both β⁻ and high-energy γ radiation (1.17 and 1.33 MeV), posing substantial long-term radiological hazards. As an alternative, Ni is widely used in AFA steels to stabilize the FCC/austenitic phase. While certain Ni

isotopes ⁵⁹Ni and ⁶³Ni have long half-lives (up to 76,000 or 100 years), they primarily emit β⁻ radiation and negligible γ radiation. Mn, another common alloying element, also produces β⁻ and γ emissions (0.85–2.1 MeV) upon activation. However, its primary radioactive isotope, ⁵⁶Mn, has a short half-life of approximately 3 h, and Mn is typically used in low concentrations to avoid the formation of brittle intermetallic phases. Al and Cr, essential for the formation of a protective alumina scale, also exhibit activation. ²⁸Al emits β⁻ and γ radiation (1.78 MeV) with a half-life of 2.25 min, while ⁵¹Cr emits γ radiation (320 keV) with a half-life of 27.7 days. Nevertheless, their short-lived isotopes and relatively low radiological hazard render them acceptable for nuclear-grade alloys. Fe, the base element in AFA steels and many FCC HEAs, produces β⁻ and γ radiation (~1.1 MeV) with a half-life of 44.5 days. Despite this, its activation profile is considered manageable, supporting its continued use. Conversely, Nb is an element commonly added in AFA steels to improve the adherence of the alumina protective scale and enhance creep strength [35,36], but it has a long half-life (~20,300 years) of its radioactive isotopes ⁹⁴Nb and persistent β⁻ and γ emissions (~0.7 MeV), which contribute to long-term radioactive waste. Even if its emission intensity is lower than that of Co, its activation behavior under irradiation cannot be ignored.

Considering the constraints required for the protective scale formation and the irradiation behavior of individual elements, the HEA candidate was designed using the CALPHAD method and the TCHEA6 Thermo-Calc thermodynamic database. The objective was to develop a thermally stable alloy across a wide temperature range. At high temperatures, where atomic mobility and transformation kinetics are fast, the alloy was designed to suppress the formation of secondary phases, ensuring structural stability under extreme conditions. In contrast, at lower temperatures, where diffusion is slower, the design allowed for the controlled formation of intermetallic phases such as L1₂, which can enhance mechanical properties, or B2, which has minimal effects on the mechanical properties [37]. The sigma phase formation was shifted to low temperatures as much as possible, to minimize its negative impact in the mechanical properties [38,39]. The resulting phase diagram is shown in Fig. 1 for the experimental (at%) composition in Table 1.

It is important to highlight that this HEA was designed using a more flexible approach compared to conventional HEAs. In this work, we define HEAs as multicomponent alloys containing five or more principal elements in significant proportions, designed to form stable solid solutions and/or tailored phase configurations, rather than strictly equiatomic compositions. This definition is consistent with the concept discussed by Li and Raabe [40], which proposes relaxing the original restrictions of the HEA concept, such as the requirement for equiatomic ratios and exclusive single-phase structures, and emphasizes property optimization over entropy maximization. As noted by Li and Raabe [40], the formation of single-phase solid solutions in HEAs shows only weak dependence on maximizing configurational entropy through equiatomic ratios of elements, and achieving maximum entropy is not the most critical factor when developing multicomponent alloys with superior properties. Together, these insights have led to a broader design space that allows non-equiatomic compositions and multiphase configurations. Following this rationale, the alloy investigated in this study (Fe_{33.5}Ni_{43.5}Cr₁₁Mn₆Al₆) was intentionally designed as a non-equiatomic HEA in order to exploit the expanded compositional space and enable tailored phase stability and mechanical performance. This approach aims to combine solid-solution strengthening with

Fig. 1. CALPHAD phase diagram for the experimental $\text{Fe}_{33.5}\text{Ni}_{43.5}\text{Cr}_{11}\text{Mn}_6\text{Al}_6$ HEA composition, predicted using the TCHEA6 Thermo-Calc thermodynamic database.

potential multiphase effects, which aligns with modern design strategies that prioritize property optimization over strict entropy-based criteria.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Initial microstructure

Fig. 2(a) shows a representative backscattered electron (BSE) image obtained by SEM of the bulk material after the annealing heat treatment, which reflects the characteristic microstructure observed in most of the analyzed regions. These micrographs show a high number of annealing twins. Besides, some localized areas, defects such as those shown in Fig. 2(b) and Fig. 2(c) were identified. Specifically, Fig. 2(b) reveals the presence of frequent oxides (black dots), which could potentially compromise the corrosion resistance of the alloy. Additionally, Fig. 2(c)

highlights less frequent regions exhibiting a bimodal-grained microstructure with certain proportion of coarse grains and fine grains, which may also influence locally both, corrosion [3] and plastic deformation behavior.

An XRD analysis was performed on the annealed condition to evaluate the phase composition and crystallographic structure of the $\text{Fe}_{33.5}\text{Ni}_{43.5}\text{Cr}_{11}\text{Mn}_6\text{Al}_6$ alloy. The diffraction pattern shown in Fig. 2(d) is consistent with the expected crystallography of single-phase HEAs. However, a close inspection of the different reflections shows a non-standard shape characterized by varying amounts of sharp secondary peaks and/or the presence of shoulder peaks that could indicate local variation of the lattice parameters due to segregation or decomposition of the FCC phase throughout the microstructure. However, as Fig. 2 shows an average grain size bigger than $50\ \mu\text{m}$, the irradiated volume during the X-ray diffraction analysis will not contain a sufficient number

Fig. 2. (a-c) are representative SEM-BSE images of the $\text{Fe}_{33.5}\text{Ni}_{43.5}\text{Cr}_{11}\text{Mn}_6\text{Al}_6$ alloy after the annealing heat treatment. (d) XRD pattern corresponding to a fully FCC structure.

of crystallites for accurate analysis. A limited number of crystallites within the irradiated volume during XRD analysis results in poor orientation statistics, which manifest in two key effects on the diffraction pattern. First, the diffraction peaks appear discontinuous and asymmetric, with an uneven intensity distribution across the 2θ spectrum deviating from the smooth, symmetric (often Gaussian) profiles characteristic of fine-grained, randomly oriented polycrystalline materials. Second, angular divergence effects emerge due to the intrinsic divergence of the X-ray beam. Individual grains diffract at slightly offset angles, preventing optimal constructive interference and contributing to incoherent peak broadening.

An important feature of the alloy that could potentially influence liquid metal dissolution is the elemental segregation within the alloy. To evaluate the elemental distribution, EPMA mapping of the main alloying elements was performed (Fig. 3). The analysis was conducted using a 20 kV voltage and a current of 200 nA over a scanned area of $40 \times 40 \mu\text{m}$ with a step size of $0.1 \mu\text{m}^2$, a dwell time of 10 ms. A representative region containing grain boundaries (marked by black dashed lines) and twins (red dashed lines) is shown in the BSE micrograph. To facilitate the identification of elemental differences in the matrix, maximum and minimum counts associated with oxide inclusions were excluded from the EPMA maps. Overall, the EPMA results reveal no significant variations in elemental distribution. No trends were observed in association with grain boundaries or twin structures. However, localized Cr-rich concentration areas were detected (highlighted with arrows), although these do not correlate with microstructural features such as grain boundaries or twins. These anomalies may be attributed to analytical artifacts or possibly the presence of Cr carbides due to the residual carbon content present in the composition as reported in the experimental composition (Table 1).

These microstructural defects, such as frequent oxides and fine-grained recrystallized regions, could significantly influence the degradation mechanisms in liquid metal environments. In the case of LMC, oxide inclusions may act as a preferential pathway for Pb penetration, compromising the continuity of the protective scale. Likewise, fine-

grained recrystallized zones exhibit higher density of grain boundaries, which are known for being a preferential zone of localized dissolution [3].

Regarding LME, these defects can concentrate mechanical stresses and facilitate the initiation of intergranular fractures. Although EPMA did not reveal any detectable segregation associated with grain boundaries or twins, localized anomalies in the Cr map could also contribute to heterogeneity in the alloy's response to LMC and LME. Therefore, the initial characterization suggests that the alloy's microstructure may influence the behavior under LMC and LME conditions. This will be evaluated in the following sections.

4.2. Corrosion behavior in stagnant lead

In this section, the oxidation behavior and Pb penetration under stagnant conditions at $550 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 1150 h of exposure and oxygen concentration in Pb between $7.4 \cdot 10^{-6}$ to $8.6 \cdot 10^{-6}$ wt% were studied. According to the literature, under those oxygen conditions and within $400\text{--}600 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, a protective oxide scale can form in alloys without precipitating PbO [41]. In addition, the oxidation behavior and Pb penetration were studied at $650 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ at 1150 h of exposure and oxygen concentration in Pb between $4.5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ to $3.6 \cdot 10^{-4}$ wt%, which corresponds to a regime where protective scale formation becomes thermodynamically challenging. According to Müller et al. [41], the solubility limit of oxygen in liquid Pb at $650 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ is approximately $7.0 \cdot 10^{-3}$ wt%, meaning that the tested concentrations remain well below the precipitation threshold for PbO, thus avoiding oxide clogging. However, at such elevated temperatures, the increased atomic mobility and instability of certain oxide phases can hinder the formation and adhesion of protective scales. These conditions demand alloys capable of forming dense, continuous, and chemically stable oxides.

To assess oxide scale formation preliminarily, EDS line scans were performed in zones free of Pb ingress, as shown in Fig. 4(a) at $550 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 1150 h and Fig. 4(b) at $650 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 1150 h. In Fig. 4(a), the EDS profile reveals increasing O and Al counts near the surface, suggesting the

Fig. 3. SEM-BSE micrograph and corresponding EPMA elemental maps of Mn, Al, Ni, Fe, and Cr acquired in the annealed $\text{Fe}_{33.5}\text{Ni}_{43.5}\text{Cr}_{11}\text{Mn}_6\text{Al}_6$ alloy. Grain boundaries and twin boundaries are indicated by black and red dashed lines, respectively. The colorbars represent measured EPMA intensities. The presence of oxides and Cr-enrich regions has been pinpointed with arrows.

Fig. 4. Two representative regions selected at (a) 550 °C for 1150 h and (b) 650 °C for 1150 h. The a_1 and b_1 SEM-BSE micrographs show low-magnification views of the microstructure, while a_2 and b_2 SEM-BSE micrographs highlight detailed areas outlined by dashed squares. In a_3 and b_3 , EDS line scans reveal the formation of Al-rich oxide scale, along the analyzed region indicated by a red arrow in the middle micrographs.

formation of an Al-rich oxide scale. In contrast, Fig. 4(b) shows a broader O peak, indicative of a bilayer structure: an inner Al-rich oxide and an outer layer enriched in Fe and Mn.

To complement the EDS line scan results, EPMA mapping was conducted on the same regions to evaluate the continuity of the oxide scales, their progression, and Pb penetration. The EPMA map in Fig. 5(a), corresponding to the $\text{Fe}_{33.5}\text{Ni}_{43.5}\text{Cr}_{11}\text{Mn}_6\text{Al}_6$ HEA exposed at 550 °C for 1150 h, confirms the formation of a thin Al-rich oxide scale in areas without Pb ingress, consistent with the EDS results. Additionally, although the EDS line scan in Fig. 4(a) does not clearly reveal it, the EPMA maps revealed a secondary outer scale enriched in Mn, Fe, and Cr, though with lower elemental counts compared to the matrix. Elemental depletion zones adjacent to the oxide scale, particularly of Mn and Al, suggest diffusion of these elements toward the surface to form the oxide. While Al depletion appears localized, Mn depletion extends across the entire interface. Notably, in Mn-depleted regions such as grain boundaries, the enrichment of Fe and Ni was detected, but no Pb was present. This behavior, also reported in AFA steels, suggests the formation of a transitional layer that acts as an effective diffusion barrier [42]. The Pb distribution map reveals its presence within the outer Mn-Fe-Cr-rich and the inner Al-rich oxide scales, indicating that the outer scale is non-protective and prone to eventual detachment and the Al-rich oxide scale is the protective one.

On the other hand, as shown in Fig. 5(a), areas where excess oxide has formed, appearing as localized oxide nodules, show only minimal Pb penetration. These regions also exhibit Mn depletion and Ni enrichment at the interface. Nevertheless, the progression of oxidation and the alloy's self-healing capability prevent significant Ni dissolution. A clear manifestation of this self-healing behavior is the formation of a new oxide scale in the penetrated areas, enriched in Al, Cr, Mn, and O, suggesting that the alloy actively regenerates its protective barrier even after localized Pb ingress.

The EPMA map in Fig. 5(b), corresponding to the $\text{Fe}_{33.5}\text{Ni}_{43.5}\text{Cr}_{11}\text{Mn}_6\text{Al}_6$ HEA exposed at 650 °C for 1150 h, reveals several similarities with the results obtained at 550 °C for 1150 h. Notably, Mn and Al depletion zones are again observed, accompanied by Fe and Ni enrichment at the interface, features indicative of a protective

oxide scale. However, at 650 °C, the depletion zones are more extensive, reflecting increased elemental mobility at such higher temperature.

The Al map shows a thicker Al-rich oxide scale as compared to the $\text{Fe}_{33.5}\text{Ni}_{43.5}\text{Cr}_{11}\text{Mn}_6\text{Al}_6$ HEA exposed at 550 °C for 1150 h, particularly in regions affected by Pb penetration, while the O map reveals an even more pronounced oxide layer that correlates with Mn and, to a lesser extent, Fe signals. These observations support the formation of a bilayer oxide structure: an inner Al-rich layer and an outer Mn-Fe-Cr-rich layer, consistent with the EDS line scan in Fig. 4(b).

Additionally, Cr enriched precipitates appear between the Al-rich oxide scale and the interface, especially in areas where the bilayer is thicker or where Pb ingress has occurred. Similar Cr enrichment has been reported in AFA steels [42,43] and HEAs [25], and is likely driven by elemental diffusion during oxidation. Cr-enrich precipitates are also visible in the bulk that could be carbides of the type M_{23}C_6 (with $\text{M}=\text{Cr}$), based on the thermodynamic calculations (Fig. 1). As observed at 550 °C, Pb is present within both oxide layers at 650 °C, reinforcing the conclusion that only the inner Al-rich oxide scale is protective.

Interestingly, as shown in Fig. 5(b), the oxide nodule visible at 650 °C consists of a thick inner Al-rich oxide overlain by a Mn-rich oxide scale. Although Pb is detected within the nodule, its presence remains confined to the oxide and does not indicate efficient penetration into the alloy. A faint Ni signal is observed at the interface, suggesting that Ni dissolution did not occur. These findings confirm that the alloy's self-healing capability remains effective even in regions affected by localized oxidation.

Finally, B2-type precipitates, which are enriched in Ni, Mn, and Al are also visible in the bulk of these aged samples, as indicated by arrows in the corresponding EPMA map in Fig. 5(b). This phase is predicted by the thermodynamic calculations (Fig. 1) during ageing at 650 °C but not at 550 °C.

To quantify the coverage of localized surface imperfections (oxide nodules), low-magnification SEM-BSE micrographs spanning the gauge surfaces (Supplementary Figure S1) were obtained. The analysis yields a surface defect fraction of 0.072 ± 0.083 at 550 °C and 0.074 ± 0.037 at 650 °C. Across the two specimens examined at each temperature, this small difference does not indicate a significant temperature dependence.

Fig. 5. SEM-BSE micrographs and EPMA elemental maps of the $Fe_{33.5}Ni_{43.5}Cr_{11}Mn_6Al_6$ HEA exposed to stagnant liquid Pb at 550 °C for 1150 h (a) and 650 °C for 1150 h (b), showing distributions of Fe, Ni, Cr, Mn, Al, Pb, and O. The color bars represent measured EPMA intensities. Labels have been inserted to highlight the different features observed.

However, the larger experimental error at 550 °C suggests a more inhomogeneous distribution of oxide nodules on the surface at this temperature. While elemental redistribution (Al/Mn depletion at the metal/oxide interface and Fe/Ni enrichment) is more pronounced at 650 °C, the defect coverage remains essentially invariant, suggesting that the self-healing behavior and scale continuity compensate for the higher diffusivity at the elevated temperature.

To further identify the nature of the oxides formed on the alloy surface, GIXRD was performed on representative areas exposed at 550 °C and 650 °C for 1150 h, as shown in Fig. 6. Rietveld refinement of the diffraction data revealed peaks corresponding to the FCC matrix and a spinel-type oxide phase with the general formula $MM'_{2}O_{4}$. In this structure, M cations occupy tetrahedral sites (e.g., Fe^{2+} and Mn^{2+}), while M' cations occupy octahedral sites (Fe^{3+} and Cr^{3+}). This spinel-type oxide is consistent with the bilayer structure observed in the EDS line scans (Fig. 4) and EPMA maps (Fig. 5), where an outer Mn-rich oxide layer, likely $Mn(Fe,Cr)_{2}O_{4}$, is formed over an inner Al-rich oxide scale. Notably, the alumina layer was not detected by GIXRD, likely due to its position beneath the irradiated surface volume analyzed by the X-ray beam. This limitation highlights that the detected phases correspond only to the uppermost region of the surface and do not represent the full depth of the oxide scale.

Based on the combined EDS, EPMA and XRD analysis, the non-equiatomic $Fe_{33.5}Ni_{43.5}Cr_{11}Mn_{6}Al_{6}$ HEA demonstrated the ability to form a bilayer oxide scale under stagnant liquid Pb exposure at both 550 °C and 650 °C, consisting of an inner Al-rich oxide layer and an outer $Mn(Fe,Cr)_{2}O_{4}$ spinel oxide. EPMA analyses confirmed that only the inner Al-rich oxide scale acts as a diffusion barrier against Pb ingress, while the outer spinel is non-protective and prone to detachment. At the areas where Pb penetration took place, the alloy exhibited self-healing behavior, with the regeneration of a new Al-, Cr-, Mn- and Fe-enriched oxide scale even after localized Pb penetration. These findings reinforce the importance of designing oxide scales that are thin, dense, and continuous to ensure long-term protection in HLM.

Remarkably, at 650 °C, where the formation of a stable protective scale is typically more challenging due to increased elemental mobility and oxide instability, the alloy still developed a protective Al-rich oxide layer. H. Shi et al. study demonstrated that at 650 °C, only AFA steels (~23 wt% Ni) are alloys capable of forming a protective scale in molten Pb, above those values alloys suffer from dissolution attack, not being able to form a protective scale [42]. This result highlights the robustness of the $Fe_{33.5}Ni_{43.5}Cr_{11}Mn_{6}Al_{6}$ HEA scale and the alloy's capacity to maintain its integrity, despite its Ni content being twice as high (~46 wt%).

Moreover, based on the extensive Mn depletion and its presence throughout the Al-rich oxide layer, it is reasonable to infer a synergistic role of Mn in promoting Al-rich oxide scale formation. This effect has also been observed in Mn-containing AFA steels, where Mn-rich alumina scales were formed after long-term oxidation at 700–800 °C [12].

Fig. 6. GIXRD of the $Fe_{33.5}Ni_{43.5}Cr_{11}Mn_{6}Al_{6}$ HEA oxide surface formed on the area exposed to stagnant liquid Pb at 550 °C and 650 °C for 1150 h.

The most significant outcome of this study is that, despite the relatively low Al content (2.8 ± 0.1 wt%/ 5.7 ± 0.2 at%) and a high Ni content (46.7 ± 0.4 wt%/ 43.7 ± 0.4 at%), approximately three times higher than that of typical AFA steels, it was still possible to form a stable and protective oxide scale that effectively prevents Ni dissolution. This highlights the potential of the $Fe_{33.5}Ni_{43.5}Cr_{11}Mn_{6}Al_{6}$ HEA as a candidate material for high-temperature nuclear applications in Pb-cooled systems.

To confirm the bilayer architecture inferred from EPMA and GIXRD characterization techniques, which consists of an inner Al-rich barrier and an outer $Mn(Fe,Cr)_{2}O_{4}$ spinel, and to resolve features below EPMA's spatial resolution, a site-specific cross-sectional TEM analysis has been performed on FIB-extracted lamellae from representative regions of the oxidized surface at 550 °C-1150h and 650 °C-1150h. Prior to milling, a Pt/C protective cap was deposited to preserve the near-surface oxide. Representative FIB-SEM SE micrographs of the extracted lamellae are provided in Supplementary Figure S2. From each lamella, regions free of major preparation artifacts were selected for detailed HAADF-STEM imaging, HR-TEM imaging, EDX mapping and normalized intensity line scans. At 550 °C, HAADF-STEM and the corresponding EDX elemental maps (Fig. 7(a)), together with normalized line scans (Fig. 7(b) and Fig. 7(c)), reveal a bilayer oxide at the alloy surface with an overall thickness of ~50–100 nm. The inner layer is Al-rich (~20–30 nm) and directly adjacent to the bulk alloy; the outer layer is enriched in Mn, Fe, and Cr (~30–70 nm). The low thickness is normally associated with greater adhesion of the oxide scale so that no spallation occurs, thus promoting corrosion resistance [44]. However, HR-TEM of the inner Al-rich scale (Fig. 7(d) and Fig. 7(e)) shows no discernible lattice fringes, suggesting an amorphous character that would explain its non-detection by GIXRD and supports the interpretation of an early-stage alumina capable of transforming into $\alpha-Al_2O_3$ upon longer exposure or at higher temperature [12,45]. Within the outer oxide, the EDX maps and line scans show compositional zoning across the thickness: the sublayer closer to the alumina showed Al-Mn-Cr enrichment (consistent with $Mn(Cr,Al)_2O_4$) in Fig. 7(b) and Mn-Cr enrichment (consistent with $MnCr_2O_4$) in Fig. 7(c) revealing that Al can be detected in some regions of the inner spinel, whereas the most exterior sublayer is Mn-Fe-rich (consistent with $MnFe_2O_4$). Attempts to acquire Selected Area Electron Diffraction (SAED) patterns from the thin oxide were unsuccessful because the selected-area aperture unavoidably included portions of the Pt/C cap and the underlying metal; nevertheless, local HR-TEM regions exhibit multiple lattice fingerprints within the outer oxide, consistent with a polycrystalline spinel.

At 650 °C, HAADF-STEM/EDX (Fig. 8(a)) and normalized line scans (Fig. 8(b) and Fig. 8(c)) reveal a thicker bilayer oxide with an overall thickness of ~150–200 nm. An Al-rich inner layer (~40–50 nm) is also visible next to the interface, and Al is also detected in portions of the outer oxide, which is consistent with the broader Al-depletion zone observed by EPMA at 650 °C compared to 550 °C. As at the lower temperature, HR-TEM of the inner Al-rich layer (Fig. 8(d)) shows no significant lattice fringes, confirming its amorphous nature and explaining its absence in GIXRD. The outer oxide exhibits a continuous Mn signal across the thickness, while Cr, Al and Fe display graded distributions. Immediately above the amorphous alumina, an inner Mn-Cr spinel domain is observed (consistent with $MnCr_2O_4$). Based on the line scans, beyond the $MnCr_2O_4$ scale, the formation of oxides seems to be erratic, showing the alternation of Al-Mn regions with Fe-Mn, indicative of $MnAl_2O_4$ and $MnFe_2O_4$ spinels, respectively. However, the outermost non-detached scale typically presents a strong terminal Mn-Fe peak in the line scans, suggesting an $MnFe_2O_4$ termination. The erratic behavior of Al and Fe with Mn observed between the line scan in Fig. 8(b) and Fig. 8(c) beyond the $MnCr_2O_4$ can potentially be related to detection of non-homogeneous scale formation, or oxide nodules. It is important to highlight that based on the line scan and the EDX maps, Cr, opposite to what it could be observed for Al, is only present at the inner spinels, the ones next to the amorphous scale. As at 550 °C, SAED acquisition was

Fig. 7. Cross-section TEM of the oxide scale formed after exposure in liquid Pb at 550 °C for 1150 h. (a) HAADF-STEM overview with corresponding EDX elemental maps (Al, Mn, Fe, Cr, O), (b-c) Normalized EDX line scans across the oxide scale showing compositional gradients and (d-e) HR-TEM of the inner Al-rich layer and the outer spinel. White/black dashed lines in micrographs d) and e) are drawn approximately to differentiate between oxide scales, and serve only as a visual guide.

not feasible due to the limited thickness and multiplicity of phases, but HR-TEM micrographs (Fig. 8(e)) show varied lattice fringes consistent with a polycrystalline spinel mixture.

Across both temperatures, Cr-rich precipitates are observed near the

metal/oxide interface; at 550 °C they are below EPMA's spatial resolution used, while at 650 °C they are larger and not uniformly distributed over the surface. Supplementary HAADF-STEM/EDX cases (Figure S3) confirm their O, Cr, and Mn enrichment, supporting identification as

Fig. 8. Cross-section TEM of the oxide scale formed at 650 °C for 1150 h. (a) HAADF-STEM overview with corresponding EDX elemental maps (Al, Mn, Fe, Cr, O), (b-c) Normalized EDX line scans across the oxide showing compositional gradients and (d-e) HR-TEM of the inner Al-rich layer and the outer spinel. White dashed line in micrograph d) is drawn approximately to differentiate between bulk and Al oxide scale, and serve only as a visual guide.

MnCr_2O_4 . In addition, Ni can be detected at 550 °C within the outer spinel domains and at 650 °C locally within both the amorphous alumina and the spinel, suggesting Ni trapping during oxide growth.

TEM evidences at 550 and 650 °C demonstrate a robust and

temperature-dependent bilayer architecture: a thin amorphous alumina inner barrier and a polycrystalline outer spinel over layer whose chemistry changes gradually from Mn-Cr near the alumina (MnCr_2O_4) to Mn-Fe at the surface (MnFe_2O_4), with Al-bearing spinel domains

appearing at 650 °C.

4.3. Phase stability at high temperatures

Minimizing the impact of phase transformations at high temperatures is essential to avoid aggravating LMC, which can be exacerbated by elemental diffusion and microstructural instability.

At 550 °C, as shown in Fig. 5 and confirmed by XRD analysis (Fig. 9), no secondary phases were detected in the bulk material, indicating that the FCC matrix remained stable throughout the exposure period. However, the Vickers microhardness values measured on the annealed material ($HV_1=137 \pm 3$) and after exposure at 550 °C for 1150 h ($HV_1=212 \pm 4$) revealed a significant hardening. According to thermodynamic calculations in Fig. 1 this hardening could be attributed to the formation of $L1_2$ nano-precipitates, which are known to substantially enhance the strength of HEAs [46]. These phases, combined with the formation of a continuous Al-rich oxide scale, reinforce the alloy's potential for long-term performance in Pb environments.

At 650 °C, Cr-rich precipitates were observed at grain boundaries and within the matrix, which according to the thermodynamic calculations are $M_{23}C_6$. On the other hand, as indicated in the EPMA maps in Fig. 5(b), some B2 phases, rich in Mn, Ni and Al, can be observed at the grain boundaries, which were also identified via XRD (Fig. 9). According to TCHEA6 thermodynamic database of Thermo-Calc software, these precipitates correspond to $(Ni,Mn)Al$. Even though thermodynamic calculations shown in Fig. 1 do not predict the presence of $L1_2$ at this temperature, the microhardness still increased to $HV_1=200 \pm 5$ after 1150 h at 650 °C. Interestingly, studies by Bin Hu et al. on AFA steels aged at 700 °C revealed that the maximum strengthening effect of $L1_2$ nano-precipitates occurs within the first 24 h [47]. This rapid precipitation kinetics was also observed in the present alloy, as evidenced by the microhardness value of $HV_1=178 \pm 5$ after just 24 h, an increase of 41 HV_1 units compared to the annealed condition, confirming the $L1_2$ nano-precipitation even though it was not thermodynamically predicted by the TCHEA6 thermodynamic database of Thermo-Calc.

These microstructural features suggest a complex interplay between oxidation, elemental redistribution, and phase evolution. Importantly, their presence did not compromise the protective behavior of the oxide scale. On the contrary, B2-type precipitates may contribute positively to corrosion resistance by acting as Al reservoirs, facilitating the outward diffusion of Al and supporting the formation and maintenance of the protective alumina scale [48–50] while having minimal effects on mechanical properties in terms of strength [37]. In addition, the presence of $L1_2$ nano-precipitates can significantly enhance the mechanical properties [46,47].

Furthermore, regardless of the exposure conditions, no deleterious phases such as sigma or laves, commonly observed in many AFA steels, were formed, which could otherwise weaken the matrix.

Fig. 9. XRD pattern corresponding to the $Fe_{33.5}Ni_{43.5}Cr_{11}Mn_6Al_6$ HEA bulk material after the treatment at 550 °C for 1150 h and 650 °C for 1150 h.

Overall, the observed phase stability at both temperatures, along with the beneficial role of B2 precipitates, supports the alloy's suitability for high-temperature applications in Pb-cooled environments. Nevertheless, further studies involving longer exposure times under those conditions are necessary to fully assess the thermal stability of these alloys.

4.4. Embrittlement behavior under liquid lead exposure

Fig. 10 presents the engineering stress-strain curves obtained under SSRT conditions, while Fig. 11 summarizes the evolution of Yield Strength (YS), Ultimate Tensile Strength (UTS), and uniform elongation (UEL) with temperature in both environments.

As shown by the engineering stress-strain curves in Fig. 10, differences in mechanical properties among tensile tests performed under identical conditions are attributed to microstructural heterogeneities, particularly the presence of randomly distributed fine-grained regions in the material annealed at 925 °C. Variations between coarse- and fine-grained areas, and the associated differences in grain boundary density and their effect on dislocation slip, lead to scatter in YS, UTS, and elongation values according to the Hall-Petch effect. This scatter is further amplified by the very small specimen dimensions, which enhance the influence of local grain-size variability on flow and fracture. It is worth noting that specimens pre-exposed to 450 °C for approximately 20–22h in Pb did not exhibit any significant hardening, as confirmed by Vickers microhardness measurements ($HV_1=137 \pm 3$ in the annealed condition and $HV_1=147 \pm 2$ after pre-exposure). This behavior is attributed to the slow formation kinetics of the $L1_2$ nano-precipitates at this temperature. For this reason, Ar was used as an inert control atmosphere without any pre-exposure treatment.

As observed in Fig. 11 (a), the YS remains within a narrow range across the tested temperatures, indicating minimal influence of the environment and confirming that the alloy maintains its mechanical integrity even at elevated temperatures. In contrast, the UTS (Fig. 11 (b)) and UEL (Fig. 11 (c)) exhibit a clear decreasing trend with increasing temperature. Up to 400 °C, the stress-strain curves in Fig. 10 (c) show high ductility and similar behavior in Pb and Ar, with no signs of LME, as reflected by the nearly overlapping curves and stable elongation values, which is also consistent with the proximity of UTS and elongation values in Fig. 11 (b-c).

At 500 °C, however, a sharp reduction in UEL and UTS occurs in Pb, while Ar-tested samples retain higher values, marking the onset of embrittlement as shown in Fig. 11 (b-c). This divergence is also evident in the stress-strain curves in Fig. 10 (d), where Pb-exposed specimens fail earlier and without reaching the UTS, a clear indication of the fragility induced by liquid metal. At the highest temperature, both environments show reduced ductility, but the degradation is significantly more severe in Pb, confirming that LME becomes dominant under these conditions.

These results highlight that while thermal effects contribute to the overall loss of ductility, the combined effect of temperature and liquid Pb exposure accelerates embrittlement beyond what is observed in the inert environment. For samples exposed to Pb, the degradation occurs earlier, reinforcing the role of LME. However, this reduction may also be influenced by thermally activated mechanisms that take place even in Ar, such as the temperature-induced phase transformations (e.g., precipitation reactions). This interpretation is supported by Vickers microhardness measurements undertaken on the clamping area of the 600 °C SSRT sample (not subjected to deformation during the experiment), which showed $HV_1=187 \pm 1$ compared with the $HV_1=147 \pm 2$ after 22 h at 450 °C. Thermodynamic calculations (Fig. 1) suggest that this hardening at 600 °C is likely due to the rapid $L1_2$ precipitation during the SSRT experiment.

An additional feature observed in the mechanical behavior of this alloy is that the strain-hardening behavior at the lower temperatures is comparable to that of some austenitic steels. This behavior is generally attributed to the low stacking fault energy (SFE). A low SFE promotes

Fig. 10. Engineering stress-strain curves of HEA obtained from SSRT tests at (a) RT (b) 350 °C, (c) 400 °C, (d) 500 °C, (e) 580/600 °C. For each temperature, two curves are shown: test curves under the Ar inert atmosphere in blue and test curves under liquid Pb in red. Solid and dashed lines represent two independent tests under identical conditions.

the dissociation of dislocations into partials and the formation of wide stacking faults, which hinder cross-slip and lead to significant strain hardening. At room temperature, cross-slip of perfect dislocations is energetically unfavorable; combined with wide stacking faults from low SFE, would explain the high work-hardening observed. This behavior has been extensively described in austenitic steels, where the SFE critically governs the transition between dislocation glide, twinning, and martensitic transformation mechanisms [51]. In this regard, for the better understanding of the results shown in Fig. 10, the SFE of $\text{Fe}_{33.5}\text{Ni}_{43.5}\text{Cr}_{11}\text{Mn}_6\text{Al}_6$ HEA was calculated using the Olson and Cohen's thermodynamic model [52] using Eq. 1.

$$\text{SFE} = 2\rho\Delta G^{\text{FCC}\rightarrow\text{HCP}} + 2\sigma^{\text{FCC}/\text{HCP}} \quad (1)$$

Where the molar surface density (ρ) is $2.97 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ mol/m}^2$, the Gibbs free energy for FCC→HCP transformation was calculated using the CALPHAD approach by using Thermo-Calc® 2023b software with TCHEA6 database. The surface energy between the FCC and HCP ($\sigma^{\gamma/\epsilon}$) was assumed to be $11.5 \pm 3.5 \text{ mJ/m}^2$ similar to the one reported for Fe-Cr-Ni alloys [52]. The SFE calculated using Eq. 1 is $45 \pm 7 \text{ mJ/m}^2$. Since this is a preliminary calculation, it was performed without considering the strain energy which would, anyhow, increase this value. While SFE calculations suggest that deformation twinning is unlikely in this alloy,

Fig. 11. Temperature Evolution of the (a) Yield Strength, (b) Ultimate Tensile Strength, and (c) Uniform Elongation of the Fe_{33.5}Ni_{43.5}Cr₁₁Mn₆Al₆ HEA under SSRT conditions in Pb and Ar environments. The dashed lines have been drawn as a guide to the eye.

its contribution cannot be entirely ruled out. Twinning may occur after a certain strain threshold or in localized regions with lower SFE, as observed in other HEAs. Although no direct microstructural evidence has been obtained in this study, the hypothesis remains plausible and will be investigated in future work.

Besides, the marked reduction in ductility observed in Fig. 11 (b-c) above 500 °C can be explained by the activation of cross-slip due to the increase in SFE at intermediate temperatures. Under these conditions, perfect dislocations glide and cross-slip becomes the most efficient mechanism for strain-energy release, facilitating dislocation

rearrangement into cells. Consequently, strain hardening saturates rapidly, strain localizes, and necking occurs, reducing total elongation. This behavior is consistent with intermediate-temperature embrittlement (ITE): the SFE increase with temperature activates cross-slip, accelerates cell formation, saturates strain-hardening, and promotes early localization. Additionally, plastic instabilities resembling Portevin-Le Chatelier (PLC) effects were observed at intermediate temperatures. Although the alloy lacks significant interstitial elements, this behavior may be attributed to solute-dislocation interactions, as reported in the literature for similar HEAs [53].

Fig. 12. Fractographic analysis of Fe_{33.5}Ni_{43.5}Cr₁₁Mn₆Al₆ specimens tested under SSRT conditions at RT (25 °C) in the Ar atmosphere. Fractography a corresponds to the full fracture surface at lower magnification, while fractography b shows a higher magnification view. Regardless of the exposure environment these images highlight the presence of dimples.

To further elucidate the mechanical response and failure mechanisms, fractographic analyses were conducted on one representative specimen from each condition, as shown in Fig. 12 at RT (25 °C), Fig. 13 for 350 °C, Fig. 14 for 400 °C, Fig. 15 for 500 °C, and Fig. 16 for 580/600 °C.

In the reference condition at RT, Fig. 12, ductile features can be identified. At lower magnification, Fig. 12 (a), it is possible to see necking with a cone shape, and at higher magnification, Fig. 12 (b), the presence of dimples indicative of microvoid coalescence (MVC).

At 350 °C, both Pb-, Fig. 13 (a₁₋₂), and Ar-exposed samples, Fig. 13 (b₁₋₂), depict ductile fracture features similar to the ones observed at RT. SEM images in this figure suggest pronounced necking and MVC in the two environments, confirming that LME is not active at this temperature.

At 400 °C, ductile behavior persisted in both environments. The Pb-exposed specimen showed necking and dimples in the initiation and propagation zones, with some intergranular features appearing in the final fracture region. High-magnification images (Fig. 14 (a₄)) revealed smeared and dragged regions rather than flat cleavage planes, suggesting plastic deformation dominated the failure. The Ar-exposed sample (Fig. 14 (b₁₋₂)) showed similar ductile features, consistent with the behavior observed at 350 °C. However, it is important to note that the stress-strain curves at 400 °C in Pb are nearly identical to those obtained in Ar, indicating that the overall mechanical response remains ductile. This suggests that the brittle fracture features observed may be localized effects driven by microstructural heterogeneities rather than a full manifestation of LME.

At 500 °C, a clear transition to brittle behavior was observed in the Pb-exposed specimen (Fig. 15(a₁₋₄)). SEM analysis showed a complete absence of necking and a fracture surface dominated by transgranular cleavage (Fig. 15(a₂)), with some regions containing isolated dimples (Fig. 15(a_{3,4})). These features suggest that Pb penetration into the

matrix weakened metallic bonds, promoting both intergranular and transgranular fracture. The Ar-exposed specimen (Fig. 15(b₁₋₂)) retained ductile characteristics, including necking and dimples consistent with MVC.

At 580/600 °C, embrittlement intensified in the Pb-exposed sample (Fig. 16(a₁₋₂)), with fracture surfaces showing extensive brittle features and no ductile contribution. The Ar-exposed specimen (Fig. 16(b₁₋₂)) exhibited a ductile failure with some punctual brittle features.

Fractographic evidence supports the mechanical data, confirming that the Fe_{33.5}Ni_{43.5}Cr₁₁Mn₆Al₆ HEA is resistant to LME up to 400 °C, with embrittlement becoming evident at temperatures above 500 °C. In contrast, studies conducted by C. Petersson et al. on alumina-forming austenitic (AFA) steels using the same SSRT rig [10] reported signs of LME only at temperatures exceeding 570 °C in liquid Pb. Although the onset of LME in AFA steels occurs at higher temperatures compared to the Fe_{33.5}Ni_{43.5}Cr₁₁Mn₆Al₆ HEA, it is noteworthy that the HEA investigated in this study contains approximately three times the Ni content (wt%) of the AFA steels. Despite the formation of a protective alumina-rich scale observed at 550 °C and 650 °C during long-term exposure, the onset of LME at 500 °C and 600 °C suggests that the protective behavior of the oxide scale strongly depends on exposure time and growth kinetics. The short duration of SSRT tests prevents the formation of a continuous, dense scale, which normally requires slow growth to achieve a crack and pore free structure [14]. Additionally, the lower oxygen concentration 10⁻¹¹ wt% compared to long-term corrosion tests further delays the development of a protective alumina layer, highlighting the combined effect of time and oxygen availability on scale formation.

To complement the fractographic analysis and further investigate the occurrence of LME at 500 °C and 600 °C, the corresponding SSRT specimens were sectioned along the RD, and the exposed cross-sections were examined by SEM-BSE. At 500 °C, the cross-sectional micrograph

Fig. 13. Fractographic analysis of Fe_{33.5}Ni_{43.5}Cr₁₁Mn₆Al₆ specimens tested under SSRT conditions at 350 °C: (a) tested in liquid Pb and (b) in Ar atmosphere. Fractographies a₁ and b₁ correspond to the full fracture surface at lower magnification, while fractographies a₂ and b₂ show a higher magnification view. Regardless of the exposure environment, these images highlight the presence of dimples.

Fig. 14. Fractographic analysis of $\text{Fe}_{33.5}\text{Ni}_{43.5}\text{Cr}_{11}\text{Mn}_6\text{Al}_6$ specimens tested under SSRT conditions at 400 °C: (a) tested in liquid Pb and (b) in Ar atmosphere. Fractographies a_1 and b_1 correspond to the full fracture surface at lower magnification, while fractographies a_2 and b_2 show a higher magnification view. Sample (b) exhibits fully ductile fracture features, whereas sample (a) shows predominantly ductile behavior with a final brittle fracture zone.

(Fig. 17 (a)) reveals a fracture profile with only a marginal contribution of necking, which is difficult to identify from the top-view fractography in Fig. 15(a₁). In contrast, at 600 °C no evidence of necking is observed (Fig. 17 (b)), indicating a fully brittle failure dominated by environmentally assisted cracking. Regardless of temperature, both conditions exhibit secondary cracks propagating from the main fracture surface, see Fig. 17 (c₁) for 500 °C and Fig. 17 (e₁) for 600 °C. Additionally, multiple crack-initiation sites were detected away from the final fracture plane, as shown in Fig. 17 (d₁) at 500 °C and Fig. 17 (f₁) at 600 °C. In some of the SEM-BSE micrographs such as Fig. 17 (c₁) or Fig. 17 (e₁) it is also possible to see a brighter signal inside the cracks which corresponds to the presence of the heavy signal that Pb has with respect to the $\text{Fe}_{33.5}\text{Ni}_{43.5}\text{Cr}_{11}\text{Mn}_6\text{Al}_6$ bulk.

To gain further insight into the failure mechanisms and to determine the crack-propagation paths, EBSD analyses were performed on the regions highlighted by the red contours in the SEM-BSE micrographs. In these areas, IPF maps oriented parallel to the RD were acquired to

correlate the crystallographic orientation with the crack trajectory and assess whether fracture proceeded along grain boundaries or by transgranular cleavage. The corresponding crystallographic orientation maps are shown in the figures labelled with the subscript “2”, which display the IPF-RD results, with marginal reconstructions performed in MTEX (MATLAB), for each of the regions previously identified in the figures with subscript “1”. Additionally, red arrows marking the locations where crack propagation was observed in the SEM-BSE images are reproduced as white arrows in the IPF-RD maps, facilitating a direct comparison between the microstructural features and the crystallographic context of the crack paths.

At 500 °C, based on the arrows in Fig. 17 (c₁) and the corresponding IPF-RD map in Fig. 17 (c₂), the secondary cracks observed on the fracture surface clearly exhibit intergranular propagation, since crack path coincides with High Angle Grain Boundaries (HAGBs). In addition, the IPF-RD gradients and deformation bands indicate significant crystal rotation and heterogeneous plastic deformation induced by tensile

Fig. 15. Fractographic analysis of $\text{Fe}_{33.5}\text{Ni}_{43.5}\text{Cr}_{11}\text{Mn}_6\text{Al}_6$ specimens tested under SSRT conditions at 500 °C: (a) tested in liquid Pb and (b) in Ar atmosphere. Fractographies a_1 and b_1 show the full fracture surface at low magnification, while a_2 , a_3 , and b_2 provide higher magnification views. Fractography a_4 corresponds to an even higher magnification of the region shown in a_3 . Sample (b) displays fully ductile fracture features, whereas sample (a) exhibits predominantly brittle fracture with some isolated dimples.

loading. However, the Kernel Average Misorientation (KAM) map, in Fig. 17 (c_3), reveals a widespread distribution of local misorientation throughout the grain. Elevated KAM values are within a range of dozens of micrometers and form continuous bands aligned with crystallographic slip systems, indicating extensive intragranular plastic deformation prior to crack propagation. Such a deformation pattern is not consistent with an LME mechanism, at least as the main failure cause. Instead, the observed KAM distribution suggests that dislocations were able to propagate and accumulate over a large volume of the material, leading to generalized plastic deformation and strain localization before fracture. In this context, the presence of liquid Pb is more likely to have acted as a secondary accelerating factor for crack initiation or final rupture, rather than as the primary embrittlement mechanism.

On the other hand, the EBSD analyses performed on the crack initiation sites at 500 °C, (Fig. 17 (d_2)) and Fig. 17 (d_3)), showed other interesting features. It is important to notice that the superficial grains

that could be observed in Fig. 17 (d_1) were not indexed, probably due to the small size of those grains and the resolution. As could be observed on the IPF-RD, the micro-cracks nucleate at HAGB, yet the features induced by the plastic deformation are not evident. However, the KAM maps in Fig. 17 (d_3) show some high KAM bands inside the grains, revealing extensive intragranular plasticity before fracture. Thus, failure cannot be described as purely HAGB decohesion and is better captured as LME assisted cracking, where Pb wetting lowers the crack-initiation threshold yet dislocation activity remains prevalent up to final instability.

Based on the EBSD results obtained from secondary cracks on the fracture surface and at crack-initiation sites at 500 °C, it is possible to conclude that the failure mechanism is not governed by a classical LME mechanism, even though cracks preferentially propagate along HAGBs. The presence of intragranular orientation gradients, extensive KAM bands, and widespread lattice rotation within the grains is evidence of significant dislocation activity and generalized plastic deformation prior

Fig. 16. Fractographic analysis of $\text{Fe}_{33.5}\text{Ni}_{43.5}\text{Cr}_{11}\text{Mn}_6\text{Al}_6$ specimens tested under SSRT conditions at: (a) 600 °C in liquid Pb and (b) 580 °C in Ar atmosphere. Fractographies a_1 and b_1 correspond to the full fracture surface at lower magnification, while fractographies a_2 and b_2 show a higher magnification view. Sample (b) displays ductile fracture with some puntual brittle features, whereas sample (a) exhibits a brittle fracture.

to fracture. Such deformation patterns are incompatible with the Adsorption-Induced Dislocation Emission (AIDE) mechanism, which requires highly localized plasticity confined to the crack-tip region, where adsorption of liquid-metal atoms weakens interatomic bonds, facilitating discrete dislocation emission events. Under AIDE-controlled LME, plastic deformation should remain narrowly concentrated at the crack tip, not broadly distributed through the grain interior [54]. Instead, the mechanical response observed at 500 °C indicates a mechanically dominated failure process, in which liquid Pb acts primarily as a secondary factor lowering the stress required for crack initiation or accelerating final rupture rather than controlling the entire fracture process through adsorption-driven decohesion.

At 600 °C, based on the arrows at the SEM-BSE in Fig. 17 (e_1) and the corresponding IPF-RD map in Fig. 17 (e_2), the secondary cracks observed on the fracture surface clearly exhibit intergranular propagation through HAGBs, with no signs of deformation bands and heterogeneous plastic deformation, opposite to what was observed at 500 °C. In addition, the corresponding KAM map in Fig. 17 (e_3) displays high-KAM rims that are narrow and concentrated along the HAGBs and near the crack tip, indicating a smaller plastic zone and intense strain localization immediately prior to instability. A similar behavior is confirmed by the analysis of crack-initiation regions, as seen on the IPF-RD in Fig. 17 (f_2), and on the KAM map in Fig. 17 (f_3) all originating at random HAGBs and triple junctions. No intragranular slip traces, deformation bands, or crystallographic steps are detected at the crack-initiation locations, reinforcing the interpretation that crack nucleation at 600 °C is governed by HAGB weakening rather than bulk plasticity, indicating that LME governs crack propagation.

The transition from the widespread intragranular misorientation observed at 500 °C to the sharply boundary-localized strain at 600 °C confirms a temperature-dependence in the fracture mechanism. Only at

600 °C does the fracture process become strongly dominated by liquid-metal-assisted intergranular cracking, driven by Pb wetting and boundary decohesion, in contrast to the mechanically dominated Pb-assisted cracking observed at 500 °C.

5. Conclusions

This study demonstrates the promising performance of the $\text{Fe}_{33.5}\text{Ni}_{43.5}\text{Cr}_{11}\text{Mn}_6\text{Al}_6$ HEA developed to combine low activation under irradiation with the ability to form a protective scale, and microstructural stability under conditions relevant to LFRs. Despite its relatively low Al content and high Ni concentration, factors typically associated with increased solubility in liquid Pb, the alloy successfully formed a stable and protective amorphous alumina scale. This scale effectively prevented Ni dissolution during long-term exposure at both 550 °C and 650 °C.

- During long-term exposure in stagnant liquid Pb at 550 °C and 650 °C, the alloy developed a bilayer oxide consisting of an inner amorphous alumina layer and an outer polycrystalline spinel. At 550 °C, the outer spinel corresponds predominantly to $\text{Mn}(\text{Fe}, \text{Cr})_2\text{O}_4$, whereas at 650 °C it transitions to a more chemically complex $\text{Mn}(\text{Fe}, \text{Cr}, \text{Al})_2\text{O}_4$. EPMA, TEM and GIXRD confirm this temperature-dependent evolution. The outer spinel is non-protective and prone to local detachment, while the amorphous alumina layer acts as the effective diffusion barrier against Pb ingress. In regions previously contacted by Pb, the alloy regenerated an Al-rich barrier together with the spinel overlayer, indicating self-healing and reinforcing long-term corrosion resistance.
- The initial FCC annealed microstructure evolved into an FCC with L_{12} nanoprecipitates for the 550 °C condition while at 650 °C B2-

Fig. 17. SEM-BSE cross-sectional micrographs of the fracture tip of the $\text{Fe}_{33.5}\text{Ni}_{43.5}\text{Cr}_{11}\text{Mn}_6\text{Al}_6$ SSRT specimens tested at 500 °C (a) and 600 °C (b). From the surface regions shown in (a) and (b), higher-magnification BSE images highlighting secondary cracks were acquired in (c₁) and (e₁), respectively, while crack-initiation sites are shown in (d₁) and (f₁). The corresponding images with subscript “2” display the IPF-RD maps, and those with subscript “3” present the KAM maps.

type (Ni,Mn)Al precipitates were detected, which may act as Al reservoirs without compromising mechanical properties but also precipitating L1₂ nanoprecipitates, which significantly enhances the mechanical properties at both conditions.

- SSRT revealed that, despite the high Ni content, the extremely low oxygen concentration ($\sim 10^{-11}$ wt%) and the short exposure time, which hinder the formation of a continuous protective scale, combined with initial microstructural defects, the alloy maintained ductile behavior up to 400 °C in both Pb and Ar environments, showing no signs of LME. A clear transition to brittle fracture was observed at 500 °C and above in Pb, confirming the onset of LME. EBSD revealed that at 500 °C, despite intergranular crack initiation, extensive intragranular misorientation and KAM activity indicate a mechanically dominated failure assisted by Pb rather than classical LME. On the other hand, at 600 °C, cracks nucleated and propagated strictly along HAGBs with only narrow high-KAM rims and no intragranular deformation, demonstrating a clear transition to a liquid-metal-assisted intergranular cracking regime driven by Pb wetting.

Overall, the Fe_{33.5}Ni_{43.5}Cr₁₁Mn₆Al₆ HEA emerges as a strong candidate for structural applications in Gen IV nuclear reactors, particularly in Pb-cooled systems. Both tests are essential for LFR-relevant qualification: the combined results from static corrosion (LMC) and SSRT in liquid Pb, respectively resolving long-term oxide-scale stability and short-time, stress-assisted embrittlement show that the alloy can build a protective amorphous Al-rich alumina barrier, resist LME, and maintain phase stability, underscoring the promise of Co-free, FCC-based HEAs for advanced nuclear environments.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

David San-Martin: Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Roger Castellote-Alvarez:** Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Jose A. Jimenez:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Data curation. **Cesar Fernandez-Jimenez:** Supervision, Investigation. **Peter Szakalos:** Validation, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Data curation. **Christopher Petersson:** Validation, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Data curation. **Esteban Urones-Garrote:** Methodology, Resources, Supervision. **Isaac Toda-Caraballo:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.corsci.2026.113651](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.corsci.2026.113651).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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